

Diagnostic and Therapeutic Management of a Large Cervical Mass: A Case Report of Castleman Disease

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Introduction

Cervical lymphadenopathy is a frequent finding in ENT practice, covering a broad spectrum of infectious, inflammatory, autoimmune, and neoplastic etiologies. Rare lymphoproliferative disorders may mimic more frequent pathologies, representing a diagnostic challenge. Although clinical assessment and imaging investigations provide important guidance, definitive diagnosis often depends on histopathological evaluation. Large cervical masses may compromise vital neck structures including airway, vascular, and neural elements, creating significant challenges in therapeutic decision-making and surgical planning.

Case Presentation

We present the case of a 44-year-old male admitted with progressive dysphonia, dysphagia, and dyspnea evolving over four months, caused by a progressively enlarging left laterocervical mass. Physical examination revealed a voluminous (~12 cm), firm-elastic, depressible, non-tender mass with reduced mobility relative to deeper planes, associated with bilateral cervical lymphadenopathy. Imaging revealed a large cervical tumor without evidence of mediastinal involvement. Initial diagnostic efforts included a fine needle aspiration biopsy (FNAB) which was inconclusive. Due to the lesion's size and proximity to critical anatomical structures, definitive surgery was initially delayed. The patient subsequently developed acute respiratory failure requiring permanent tracheostomy. One month later, complete surgical excision of the mass was successfully performed. Histopathological analysis demonstrated lymphoid follicular hyperplasia with prominent hyalinized vasculature, confirming unicentric Castleman disease (hyaline-vascular subtype). Postoperative evolution was favorable, with restoration of airway function and progressive clinical improvement.

Conclusion

Castleman disease, although uncommon, should be included in the differential diagnosis of large cervical lymphadenopathy. This case emphasizes the diagnostic complexity of atypical cervical masses and underlines the essential role of complete surgical excision, which provides both definitive diagnosis and curative treatment in unicentric forms presenting with compressive symptoms.

Keywords

Cervical Mass, Castleman Disease, Lymphadenopathy, Airway Obstruction